

Optimization of the production of docosahexaenoic fatty acid by the heterotrophic microalga *Cryptocodinium cohnii* utilizing a dark fermentation effluent

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ABSTRACT

Dark fermentation is an anaerobic digestion process of biowaste, used to produce hydrogen as a fuel, which however releases high amounts of polluting volatile fatty acids in the environment. In order for the process to become more competitive, the acids stream can be utilized through conversion to high added-value docosahexaenoic acid by the microalga *Cryptocodinium cohnii*. Docosahexaenoic acid is one of the two main omega-3 fatty acids, necessary for human nutrition. The purpose of this work was to optimize the production of omega-3 fatty acids by the cells, utilizing the organic content of a dark fermentation effluent. For that purpose, the effect of different fermentation conditions was examined, such as incubation temperature, nitrogen source and concentration, the addition of chemical modulators, as well as the feeding composition. The volatile fatty acid content of the effluent was totally depleted in a fed-batch culture of the microalga, while the cells accumulated DHA in a percentage of 35.6% of total lipids, when fed with yeast extract or 34.2% when fed with ammonium sulfate. Taking into consideration the economic feasibility of the culture conditions proposed it was concluded that the use of yeast extract could be substituted by the much economic ammonium sulfate.

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1. Introduction

The uncontested and irrecoverable depletion of the earth resources has demonstrated the need for a circular economy, which will allow the utilization of waste for the production of high added-value substances and bulk chemicals, necessary for the human society [1]. One of the most important and widely used category of chemicals in our planet is fuels. In every corner of the earth humans rely on fuels to generate energy for their daily needs. However, conventional fuels produced through petrochemical processes are becoming scarce [2]. What is more, their use is harmful for the environment and the maintenance of the current climate [3]. Therefore research is focused on the development of clean energy sources, such as hydrogen, necessary for the further proliferation of

our society.

Hydrogen can be derived from the process of dark fermentation (DF), which however produces also a waste stream of volatile fatty acids (VFA), thus polluting the environment [4]. In order to promote the biohydrogen production and allow its safe application in industrial scale, the by-products need to be successfully exploited. A promising approach is their bioconversion to high added-value omega-3 fatty acids (FA) by the microalga *Cryptocodinium cohnii*. This approach has numerous advantages. Not only it allows the elimination of the pollutants, but it also ensures their conversion to products highly useful for human society. Omega-3 FA have been proven necessary for humans, who, apart from being able to synthesize a very small amount, need to absorb them from dietary sources [5]. It has already been proven that *C. cohnii* can assimilate VFA from a DF effluent and accumulate substantial amount of one of the main ω -3 FA, namely docosahexaenoic fatty acid (DHA) [6].

The release of biohydrogen through DF, coupled with the bioconversion of the VFA waste stream, offers a biorefinery approach that promotes a circular economy. However, a proper

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circular economy must ensure that not only the final product, but also the conversion process itself, is a part of a green strategy [7]. The use of microorganisms, such as *C. cohnii*, for the bioconversion of waste ensures an environmental approach. Nevertheless, in order to fully exploit their potential and minimize environmental impact, the understanding of microbial metabolic responses under different conditions is necessary. This allows for the optimal utilization of a microorganism and the highest bioconversion yield.

Microalgae are a diverse group of microorganisms thriving in marine or fresh water ecosystems. Due to their role in the base of the food chain they are able to produce various important metabolites, including enzymes and substances of nutritional value, such as fatty acids and carotenoids [8–10]. *C. cohnii* is a heterotrophic microalga, well-known for its ability to produce high percentages of DHA, necessary for the proper cardiovascular and neural development of humans [11,12]. Different culture conditions and metabolomic techniques have been examined to unfathom and increase its ability to produce lipids [13,14]. So far it has been shown that, when *C. cohnii* is grown on glucose, a nitrogen limitation can lead to a higher intracellular lipid content [14]. Furthermore, the addition of some chemical modulators is suspected to favor lipid production by the cells [15]. Many attempts have been made to optimize the DHA production of *C. cohnii* under glucose feed. However, to the best of our knowledge, there has not been yet a complete research on the conditions that optimize the omega-3 production of the microalga under VFA feed. Such a research will allow for the optimal conversion of the DF waste stream and the economic viability of the process of biohydrogen generation.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Chemicals and microorganisms

C. cohnii ATCC® 30772™ was obtained from the American Type Culture Collection (ATCC), was cultivated and maintained according to the corresponding protocols. Chemicals used for nutrient preparation were purchased either from Sigma-Aldrich (sodium acetate, Tris base, inorganic salts, VFA) or Fluka (yeast extract (YE), concentrated HCl and H₂SO₄) or Fisher Scientific (glucose anhydrous), while the organic solvents for the experiments were purchased from Fisher Scientific (chloroform, methanol) or Carlo Erba (n-hexane). Solvents were of analytical grade unless if stated otherwise. The permeate of a DF effluent was derived from a Vegetable, Garden and Food (VGF) waste stream and delivered by the company Tecnia Research & Innovation (Spain). It consisted of 9.3 g/L of acetic acid, 6.5 g/L propionic, 3.8 g/L butyric, 3.1 g/L valeric, 1.4 g/L caproic acid and traces (<0.5 g/L) of isobutyric and isovaleric acid.

2.2. Stock cultures and precultures

Batch cultures of 50 mL ATCC 460 Medium (A2E6) were prepared in Erlenmeyer flasks and maintained for 4 days at 23 °C without stirring. Stock cultures always included ATCC 460 Medium in order to avoid any acclimation in less nutrient-rich media that would modify the alga's biological characteristics [16]. The cultures were then used as inoculum for precultures that were prepared according to the same protocol, as previously described [6]. These were used as inoculum for the different batch cultures to study the effect of different culture conditions in biomass and microbial lipid production. The inoculum each time comprised of the 10% (v/v) of the final culture volume. Batch cultures were carried out in biological duplicates and incubated for 168 h at 27 °C and 160 rpm agitation, unless if stated otherwise.

2.3. Effect of different culture conditions in microalgal growth and lipid production

2.3.1. Effect of temperature

The performance of *C. cohnii* under different cultivation temperatures was examined under batch cultivation in Erlenmeyer flasks. Seed cells of the precultures were inoculated in fresh medium, characterized as the standard medium, containing 30 g/L sodium acetate, 18.7 g/L sea salts, 2.8 g/L YE and 100 mM buffer Tris/HCl. The final volume of the cultures was 50 mL and they were incubated under different temperatures between 15 and 30 °C.

2.3.2. Effect of nitrogen source

Batch fermentations were carried out in ATCC 460 Medium, where glucose was substituted by 30 g/L sodium acetate as the main carbon source, while the medium was buffered with 100 mM Tris/HCl at pH equal to 6.5. The (NH₄)₂SO₄ present in the ATCC 460 Medium was also replaced with one of the following nitrogen sources: YE, urea (Ur), (NH₄)₂SO₄ (Am), NaNO₃ (Nt) or NH₄NO₃ (AmNt) at concentrations that ensured a final C/N ratio equal to 83 (w/w). It is important to mention that the C/N ratio was estimated taking into consideration sodium acetate as carbon source and each one of the aforementioned nitrogen sources. The nitrogen content of YE was estimated to be ca. 11% (w/w), according to the providing company. The inoculum of these batch cultures was derived directly from ATCC 460 Medium cultures grown for 4 days at 23 °C.

2.3.3. Effect of C/N ratio

In order to determinate the influence of the nitrogen availability in the medium, *C. cohnii* batch cultures with different C/N ratios were incubated for 168 h. That was the incubation time qualified for total acetate consumption by the cells, unless if the growth was strongly inhibited. The culture medium was the same used for studying the effect of different nitrogen sources. The nitrogen source used was (NH₄)₂SO₄ and the different C/N ratios were 10, 20, 50, 83, 110, 140 and 160, achieved by adjusting the concentration of ammonium ions.

2.3.4. Effect of chemical modulators

Batch cultures with fresh standard medium were inoculated with seed cells from the precultures and incubated at 27 °C under agitation. The filter-sterilized chemical modulators, ethanolamine (ETA) and salicylic acid (SA), were added in the medium at final concentrations of 152.7 mg/L and 1.0 mg/L, respectively. Their addition was carried out during the early exponential phase, after 24 h of fermentation time. The incubation continued for a total of 168 h until the total consumption of the initial acetate. A batch culture with no chemical modulators was used as a control.

2.4. Fed-batch nitrogen limiting two-stage fermentation

In order to favor both biomass and DHA production, a two-stage strategy was examined. Fed-batch cultures in two 2 L pH-auxostats (New Brunswick Scientific-BioFlo 310 Benchtop Fermentor) were carried out, according to a previously published protocol [6]. One pH-auxostat was fed with a 33% (v/v) acetic acid solution and acted as a control culture. The two-stage pH-auxostat was provided with a feed of 33% (v/v) acetic acid and (NH₄)₂SO₄ to a final C/N ratio equal to 110. After 168 h of cultivation, the feed of the two-stage pH-auxostat was changed to 33% (v/v) acetic acid with no nitrogen source, in order to create nitrogen limitation conditions inside the vessel. The feeding of the fermentors continued until 264 h, when the oxygen consumption of the control bioreactor-therefore its metabolic activity-was minimum. The feeding of acetic acid was then manually stopped allowing the complete consumption of

the carbon source inside the culture medium. After 24 h of additional incubation time (a total of 288 h) the fermentation process was terminated. The initial dry cell concentration of the bioreactors right after the inoculation was always equal to 0.3 g/L.

2.5. Fed-batch bioreactor with optimum initial growth medium

The application of the optimal conditions found in batch cultures, was carried out in a bioreactor fed with permeate of a DF effluent. The effluent was obtained from the DF of a VGF waste stream and passed through a 1200 mm-length and 70 nm-pore size ultrafiltration membrane by Tecnalia Research & Innovation (Spain). Prior to feeding, the permeate was acidified with non-fermentable HCl to a final pH equal to 2.5 and autoclaved. Two bioreactors, one operated under the optimum temperature and initial culture medium and another one operated under the standard conditions of temperature of 27 °C and initial medium of 7.5 g/L YE, 25 g/L sea salts and 15 g/L sodium acetate (control bioreactor) were inoculated, as previously described. The fermentation was carried out until the total consumption of 500 mL of the DF permeate feed was performed.

2.6. Microalgae cells harvesting

After the end of the fermentation process, either in batch or fed-batch cultures, the culture supernatant was collected and centrifuged for 7 min at 650 g. The supernatant was discarded and the cell pellets were washed with deionized (DI) water containing an equal concentration of sea salt in order to avoid any microbial membrane destruction due to osmotic phenomena. The cells were finally centrifuged to discard the washing solution, prior to freeze-drying and final storage of the dried pellets at 4 °C. The dry cell weight (DCW) was measured gravimetrically.

2.7. Cell growth and acetate consumption analysis

Daily samples of the cultures were collected and their optical density at 685 nm (OD_{685}) was measured in order to estimate cell concentration. During the pH-auxostat operation, samples of 7–15 mL in duplicates were collected, centrifuged and washed with sea-salt water, as previously described. The cells were freeze-dried and the dry biomass was measured in order to monitor the cell growth of the cultures on a daily basis.

The daily acetate or other VFA concentration of the culture medium was calculated by HPLC analysis (Shimadzu apparatus, Kyoto, Japan), according to a previously described protocol [6].

2.8. Lipid extraction and quantification and fatty acid profile analysis

The dried biomass was used for lipid extraction. The process was carried out following a modified Folch method [17], according to a previously described protocol [6]. The final extract was collected in preweighed glass tubes. After evaporation of the solvent, the total fatty acids (TFA) were calculated gravimetrically.

The dried fatty acids were then esterified into methyl esters (FAME) and analyzed in a GC-MS/GC-FID system for the determination of the lipid profile of the cells as described previously [6].

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Effect of temperature

The experimental results indicated that the best temperature for biomass growth is found in the range of 20–23 °C, while DHA

accumulation by the cells is maximized at 23 °C (Fig. 1a). The low temperature of 15 °C couldn't facilitate cell growth effectively. This result is in accordance with a report on another strain, *C. cohnii* ATCC 30555, where the growth of the cells was also inhibited at a very low temperature of 15 °C [18]. On the other hand, at this temperature, *C. cohnii* presented the highest total lipid percentage, while in the range of temperatures between 20 and 30 °C, 27 °C was found the second best. Therefore, the strain used in the present study, appears to proliferate at temperatures around 20–23 °C and accumulate lipids at either very low or a slightly higher temperature, as a result of temperature stress. Safdar et al. also examined *C. cohnii* behavior at different incubation temperatures [18]. Their strain was better grown at higher temperatures between 25 and 30 °C, but it also accumulated more lipids and DHA at the lower temperature of 20 °C. The accumulation of lipids at low temperatures is well known in oleaginous microorganisms and has been proven effective, not only for *C. cohnii* cells, but also for *Thraustochytrium* strains [19]. A possible explanation could be the utilization of lipids by the cell in order to increase membrane fluidity, which is hampered at low temperatures [12].

The results indicate that the DHA content of the cells show no significant fluctuations with the temperature, although it is obvious that it is partially decreased at very high temperatures (Table 1). This is in accordance with the general apprehension that polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) synthesis is favored at low temperatures [20]. As reported previously, it is possible that the desaturases produced by the microalga cells exhibit a higher activity at low temperatures due to an increased availability of oxygen [21]. This is also apparent in the present results, with an exception at the temperature of 15 °C. By carrying out an ANOVA analysis coupled with a Tukey test, it is clear that between the temperature range of 17–23 °C, the difference of the DHA content (%TFA) of the cells is not significant ($p = 0.32$), securing the conclusion that the DHA is indeed favored at lower temperatures. Taking into consideration the final biomass productivity, the highest DHA production, equal to 0.45 g/L was achieved for the incubation temperature of 23 °C.

3.2. Effect of nitrogen source

Nitrogen source availability is known for playing an important role in lipids production. Apart from its concentration in the medium, the form of nitrogen source affects its uptake by the cells, and therefore its availability [22]. For that reason, the examination of the best nitrogen source for DHA accumulation is a necessary step towards the optimization of the process. The batch cultures utilizing Am as nitrogen source demonstrated a relatively higher biomass production, but, most importantly, the highest DHA accumulation by the cells, equal to 43% of TFA, in comparison to the second-best source of Nt, which led to 30% DHA production (Fig. 1b). In terms of TFA percentage, YE favored the highest total lipid production, which reached 1.12 g/L in batch cultures.

According to typical microalgal culture techniques, ammonium salts are usually the best inorganic nitrogen source, since less energy is needed by the cells for its uptake [22]. However, previous research with another *C. cohnii* strain (ATCC 30555), revealed nitrates as the best nitrogen source for DHA and lipid production [23]. The difference may be attributed to the different microalga strain or the use of a different carbon source in the growth medium. In literature, glucose is the common carbon source compared to acetate utilized in the present study, which is the main component of a DF effluent [23]. Still, YE is the favored nitrogen source for most of *C. cohnii* cultivations [24]. In contrast to the present results, another study by Mendes et al., has identified YE as a better nitrogen source than the Am, when *C. cohnii* was grown on carob syrup [25]. In that

Fig. 1. Final dry cell concentration (dots), FA distribution (bars) of the cells grown in batch cultures (a) under different incubation temperatures, (b) different nitrogen sources and (c) different initial C/N ratio.

Table 1

DHA distribution of the cells grown under different incubation temperatures.

Incubation temperature (°C)	DHA content (%TFA)
15	19.3
17	29.7
20	31.0
23	33.9
27	29.3
30	29.4

case, the addition of 5 g/L YE resulted in 19% higher DHA (%TFA) than the addition of 0.05 g/L ammonium chloride. However, the benefit of YE as a nitrogen source might be the result of the addition of a much higher amount of YE than Am, since YE includes 11% (w/w) nitrogen, therefore the nitrogen added was more than 10 times higher than in the case of the ammonium. Furthermore, YE as an organic source of nitrogen, includes a considerable amount of carbon that is expected to further boost cell proliferation.

It is interesting to highlight the behavior of the cells when grown at AmNt, which consists of nitrogen in both Am and Nt forms. In this case, the fermentation results in moderate biomass and lipid production (Fig. 1b), situated between the corresponding values of the fermentations consisting only of Am or Nt. When AmNt is dissolved into water, it produces NH_4^+ and NO_3^- ions, whose final concentration in the medium is half of the corresponding concentrations when only Am or Nt is used, provided that the total nitrogen content is kept stable. Therefore, it might be hypothesized that nitrogen in the form of NH_4^+ is probably quickly assimilated by the strain, while NO_3^- is consumed later, resulting in a somewhat lower biomass yield, combining the yields of Am and Nt alone.

3.3. Effect of C/N ratio

As known in literature, lipid production of microalgae is enhanced under certain stress conditions, such as nitrogen deprivation [11]. As a result, the C/N ratio of the culture is one of the most important factors, when lipid accumulation is considered. In the present study, the best initial C/N ratio for DHA production was examined. The initial carbon concentration was decided to be the same in all batch cultures and equal to 30 g/L, which is the optimal value for biomass production in batch cultures, according to previous results [6].

As shown in Fig. 1c, an initial C/N ratio of 110 (w/w) favors the highest biomass and also lipid production, which was latter calculated to be 6.1 g/L and 1.6 g/L, respectively, after 168 h of incubation. On the contrary, the DHA content of each cell was found to be optimal at an initial C/N ratio of 83. Nevertheless, due to the higher biomass and lipid content, the final DHA production of the culture was higher at the ratio 110 reaching 0.49 g/L in comparison to 0.38 g/L of the C/N ratio of 83. It is not the first time that a relatively low C/N ratio, such as 83, is observed to favor the DHA content of the cells. Rosa et al. discovered that a ratio of C/N equal to 55 would promote a higher final DHA concentration in a culture of *Aurantiochitrium limacinum* SR21 using glucose as carbon source, when examining different ratios from 10 to 100 [26]. This observation, however, can also be attributed to the higher biomass achieved at that ratio. Another group, Ryu et al., proved that *Aurantiochytium* sp. KRS101 reached the highest DHA content of 34.2% of TFA at a lower C/N ratio equal to 20, in comparison to higher ratios of 35 or 50 [27].

Among the examined initial C/N ratios, the lipid content is maximized at the high values in the range of 110–160, which

qualifies for a low initial nitrogen concentration. This, in general, agrees with the behavior of microalgae under nitrogen limitation. A high C/N ratio coincides with a low nitrogen concentration, which is gradually consumed during the incubation, thus creating nitrogen limitation conditions. The cells respond to that by accumulating lipids. Apart from *C. cohnii*, also other microalgae species have been known to increase their lipid percentage as a result of nitrogen depletion. *Chlorella* sp. accumulated lipids under urea limitation [28], while *Aurantiochytrium* sp. strain T66 increased its lipid content from 13 to 55% of DCW [29]. The increase of lipid under nitrogen starvation has been attributed by some researchers to an accumulation of citrate by the cells when nitrogen is absent from their environment. Excess citrate is probably acting as a carrier of acetyl units that participate in lipid synthesis [30].

However, it is clear that, when ratios exceed 110 and an even higher nitrogen limitation is accomplished, growth and lipid production are negatively affected. This pattern of *C. cohnii* has also been observed by other researchers. Safdar et al. noticed that, when grown on glucose, *C. cohnii* ATCC 30555 exhibited lower lipid production under extreme nitrogen concentrations [23]. Furthermore, it is clear that extreme nitrogen starvation conditions do not favor DHA production. It has been observed that, although a very low nitrogen concentration is favorable for total lipid accumulation, it leads to a higher percentage of saturated lipids [30]. Until now, it is a controversial subject whether DHA is produced in the cell as triacylglycerols (TAG) or phosphatidylcholine [6]. Since a nutrient limitation can cause hydrolysis of phospholipids [31], it is possible that DHA is mainly accumulated as phosphatidylcholine and therefore affected negatively by extreme nitrogen depletion. The same behavior also occurs for comparatively high nitrogen concentrations.

3.4. Effect of chemical modulators

It has been observed that specific chemical substances can act as modulators to induce lipid production in microalgae, as well as specifically in *C. cohnii* cells [32]. Li et al. have concluded that the combined addition of SA and ETA in cultures of the strain *C. cohnii* ATCC 30556 has led to a 22.5% increase of the total lipids produced [15]. In this work, the same quantity of the abovementioned chemical modulators was added in the culture medium. The biomass production between the examined cultures and the control without modulators bear no differences. Therefore, it was concluded that the ETA and SA added didn't influence the growth of the cells. However, no significant difference was also observed in the lipid production, with the ETA and SA cultures exhibiting only a 2.4% increase in the final lipid production ($p = 0.305$). More specifically the batch culture with chemical modulators resulted in 1.7 g/L of TFA production in comparison to 1.6 g/L of the control culture. More evident, however, was the effect of the modulators to DHA accumulation, since they resulted in a 29.7% of DHA in TFA in comparison to 25.8% of the control culture, resulting in a statistically significant difference between the DHA contents (%TFA) ($p = 0.031$).

3.5. Fed-batch nitrogen limiting two-stage fermentation

In the industrial sector, the fermentation processes are, in their vast majority, either fed-batch or continuous. Eventually, during fermentation, there is a feeding stream that provides the culture with the necessary nutrients for further cell proliferation. Therefore, apart from examining the cultivation conditions in different batch fermentations, the optimization of the process requires also a thorough examination of the feeding composition and its effect in the fermentation process. Apart from carbon, nitrogen is a

Fig. 2. Effect of the two-stage fermentation in the production of biomass as a function of time. The results of the control bioreactor are depicted with black, while that of the two-stage bioreactor with grey.

necessary nutrient for cell growth, which however, in high doses, affects negatively the lipid accumulation. In order to overcome the competition between biomass growth and lipid production, a fermentation protocol of two stages can be adopted. The first stage ensures the provision of all necessary nutrients for cell proliferation during the exponential growth phase, while the second creates nutrient deficiency for inducing metabolite production. According to this, the addition of nitrogen in the culture, during the early exponential phase, was examined. A two-stage bioprocess with a feed of acetic acid and nitrogen, later replaced by a solely carbon feed, was operated in comparison to a control bioreactor with no nitrogen addition at any time. The results from the fed-batch fermentations exhibited a beneficial effect of the two-stage fermentation for the final biomass production of the process. More specifically, a two-stage fermentation resulted in a final production of 24.0 g/L DCW, in comparison to 20.0 g/L DCW of the control fermentation, where no nitrogen was present in the acetic acid feeding stream (Fig. 2). In general, the fed-batch fermentation allowed substantially higher biomass productivity, resulting in 2 g/L/d when the feeding stream was supplemented with nitrogen or 1.7 g/L/d without nitrogen source supplementation. Such productivities were higher compared to the batch cultures, where the highest biomass productivity was found to be 1.1 g/L/d. It is important to notice that the biomass productivity of each bioreactor wasn't constant from the first day of fermentation. Although, the final biomass production of the two-stage fermentor was higher, the daily biomass concentration of the control fermentor, without Am feed, was higher during the first 168 h of cultivation. After this period, when Am addition stopped, the biomass productivity of the two-stage bioreactor was suddenly increased. A possible explanation for this may be the inhibition of cell growth, because of a high nitrogen concentration, in the case of the bioreactor fed with ammonium. Liu et al. have observed that a high nitrogen content in the broth can provoke growth inhibition in *C. cohnii* during the first stage of culture development [24]. During the first hours, the growth medium of the two-stage fermentation included the initial YE added, as well as ammonium from the feeding process. The high nitrogen amount available may answer for a decreased growth rate until a part of it is consumed by the microalga. When the addition of Am was stopped, the residual nitrogen source allowed the further increase of biomass and prolong

the exponential growth phase of the fermentation. On the contrary, the control fermentor wasn't benefited, at any time, by the addition of a nitrogen source, and possibly entered the static growth phase quicker, after the total depletion of the initial YE. The fact that YE is indeed a mixture of various nutrients that includes organic nitrogen, may answer for the boost of biomass productivity of the control bioreactor during the first hours of fermentation, since this bioreactor had YE as the sole nitrogen source at possibly no inhibitory concentrations. The benefit that nitrogen addition offers to the biomass yield of *C. cohnii* can also be traced in the work of Rumiani et al. [33]. The researchers observed that the cell concentration of *C. cohnii* was higher at a bioreactor constantly fed with nitrogen, in comparison to one that was only partially fed with a nitrogen source.

Regarding lipid production, the control fermentation resulted in a higher TFA accumulation (%DCW) by 12% (Fig. 3) which is possibly a result of the lower nitrogen content. The DHA content of the cells didn't exhibit significant changes between the control and the two-stage bioreactor, resulting in the highest values of 41.9% and 40.9% of TFA, respectively (Fig. 3). The microbial lipid production was only analyzed after the first 144 h of fermentation, when cell concentration was significantly increased and the biomass harvested allowed a reliable measurement. However, it has been previously reported that the lipid content of the cells is increasing with the time, during the first hours of fermentation [6]. It must be noted that due to low biomass productivity, the lipid content of the cells before 216 h of fermentation is not important for industrial exploitation, since the bioprocess wouldn't be viable based on the utilization of a dry cell concentration lower than 8 g/L. Also taking into consideration the biomass and lipid production, as well as the DHA accumulation, the final DHA production of each bioreactor was calculated to be 1.7 g/L for the control and 1.8 g/L for the two-stage cultivation. It is obvious that the increase of biomass affects favorably the final DHA production of the two-stage fermentation, thus making it a better solution for an industrial application.

3.6. Utilization of a DF effluent under initial optimal conditions in a fed-batch fermentation

According to the results obtained from the series of batch experiments, the bioprocess exhibiting higher DHA production included an initial growth medium (ATCC 460) with no glucose added, Am as a nitrogen source at a final C/N ratio equal to 110 that was operated at 23 °C. The above conditions were used to operate a fed-batch fermentation, with a DF effluent feed, which would have the optimum initial conditions, as these were pointed out from the batch experiments. It should be noted that, although the optimum acetate concentration used in batch cultures was 30 g/L, the initial concentration of sodium acetate in the optimized bioreactor's growth medium was chosen to be 20 g/L instead. The reason for that was to ensure that the quick addition of effluent feeding, won't result, at any time of the fermentation process, in a final acetate concentration higher than the inhibitory 30 g/L.

The comparative fermentation process employing the above-mentioned optimized strategy compared to standard growing conditions lasted for 68 h. During the first 48 h, 500 mL of the acidified DF effluent was fed in the bioreactors, in order to maintain a stable pH under pH-auxostat mode. After the end of the feeding step, the fermentations continued for an additional period of 20 h under batch mode, aiming in the complete consumption of VFA present in DF effluent resulting in an increased pH. At the end of the process, oxygen consumption was almost zero, while pH of the culture supernatant was almost 9. In previous experiments, HPLC analysis has exhibited the stable consumption of the acetic acid of the effluent, while the other acids were accumulated. A small

Fig. 3. Effect of the two-stage fermentation in the accumulation of lipids and the fatty acid profile of the cells as a function of time in the (a) two-stage bioreactor and the (b) control bioreactor.

consumption of propionic acid was also apparent. However, 24 h after the termination of the feeding, the residues of all the VFA inside the bioreactor were totally consumed by the microalga.

It is clear that the fermentation time was shorter in comparison to the fermentation with a feed of acetic acid. Although, *C. cohnii* is capable of depleting the VFA content of the DF feeding effluent, the volume necessary for controlling the pH of the fermentation broth was significant, due to the relatively low concentration of the carbon source presented in the form of the VFA, therefore diluting many critical nutrients. In our previous study on the fed-batch fermentation strategy employing a feeding stream of DF effluent, the necessity of increasing the VFA amount was emphasized [6]. A concentrated DF effluent would increase its capacity to control the pH of the medium and therefore it would allow high cell density fermentations that are crucial for the industrial valorization of a DF effluent for the sustainable production of omega-3 fatty acids.

In contrast to the results from the batch cultures that indicated

the optimal conditions applied in the fermentation, the final biomass recovery from the optimized fermentation was less than that of the control bioreactor operating under standard conditions (Table 2). This proves the different, constantly changing environment inside a fed-batch bioreactor. The YE as nitrogen source was proven to be more favorable to biomass production than Am, in the case of the fed-batch process. This can be attributed to the fact that YE is a mixture of various micronutrients, nitrogen and also carbon. More specifically, it is estimated that the carbon content reaches almost 40% (w/w) of YE, while total nitrogen content of it is almost 11% (w/w) [34]. Therefore, it is clear that the addition of YE cannot count solely as a nitrogen source in the growth medium. This additional carbon source included in the initial medium of the control fermentation, changes the C/N ratio and may answer for the increased microalga growth observed. Taking into consideration the carbon content of the YE, the initial carbon of the medium of the control fermentation is calculated at 7.4 g/L, in contrast to 5.9 g/L of carbon in the optimized medium. The DHA content of the cells grown with Am was almost the same as the one of the cells harvested from the control fermentation, reaching the percentage of 34.2% of TFA in comparison to 35.6% of the control. However, due to the lower biomass and total lipid production, the optimized medium resulted in a 38% lower final DHA production. In order to reach a conclusion about the best conditions for a fed-batch fermentation, the total cost of the process needs to be taken into consideration. YE, a common nitrogen source in literature that was used in the control medium, is much more expensive – almost 30-folds higher-in comparison to ammonium sulfate. Since the main target of our research is the utilization of a VFA containing waste stream, the use of a cheap nitrogen source is imperative for the sustainable production of DHA, prohibiting the use of expensive additives, such as YE. Therefore, its substitution by ammonium sulfate may be beneficial in the final technoeconomic evaluation of the overall process, overcoming the lower final DHA recovery.

3.7. Fatty acid synthesis pattern

The results of microbial fatty acid distribution under fed-batch fermentation, allow drawing conclusions regarding the DHA synthesis in *C. cohnii* cells. According to Pei et al., a possible pathway for DHA production includes the desaturation of C18 fatty acid, produced through the classical FAS pathway, to C18:1 by the delta-9 desaturase [13]. In continuance, the C18:1 is converted, by other desaturation enzymes, to C18:2 and then C18:3 fatty acid, which enters the omega-3 pathway (Fig. 4). The authors suggested also that DHA might alternatively be produced directly from acetyl-CoA as a result of a multifunctional enzyme system similar to polyketide synthase (PKS pathway).

When examining the cellular fatty acid profile exported by the pH-auxostat experiments (Fig. 3), during the fermentation process, it is obvious that the percentage of DHA is increasing, while that of C18 is declining. In contrast to that, the C18:1%, that is the intermediate product, remains more or less the same. Based on this observation, and supposing the FAS pathway is responsible for DHA production, it can be assumed that during the cultivation with a feed of acetic acid, the conversion of C18 to C18:1 and the further desaturation of C18:1 happen with a similar rate. Therefore, the

Fig. 4. Possible metabolic pathway for the conversion of C18, produced through the FAS pathway, to C22:6 by *C. cohnii* (adapted from Pei et al. [13]). “E” indicates the elongases.

activity of the different desaturases doesn't seem to be affected by the continuously changing C/N ratio. This can also be confirmed by the fatty acid profiles of the batch cultures under different initial C/N ratios, where the same pattern is followed (Fig. 1c).

Contrary to the C/N ratio effect, the incubation temperature seems to be playing a more potent role to desaturation enzyme activities. During different fermentation temperatures of the batch cultures, both C18 and C18:1 fatty acid content is decreased at higher temperatures (Fig. 1a). This pattern, however, doesn't result in a higher DHA content, especially above 23 °C. It is possible that a higher temperature inhibits the activity of the desaturases and elongases that take part in the further DHA synthesis, but not that of the delta-9 and delta-12 desaturases that are responsible for conversion of C18 to C18:1 and C18:2 accordingly.

4. Conclusions

The main purpose of this work was to provide a competitive bioprocess for the further utilization of the waste stream of the biohydrogen production. For that reason, the initial optimal fermentation conditions that ensure maximum DHA recovery from a fed-batch fermentation of *C. cohnii*, under a DF effluent feed were examined. A temperature equal to 23 °C and Am as a nitrogen source, were found to be preferable for the efficient omega-3 production under batch fermentation. However, scale-up experiments following a fed-batch feeding protocol exhibited a different behavior. It seems that the constantly changing parameters affecting biomass growth and lipid production in the bioreactor need further clarification. The C/N ratio that achieved the highest DHA production was equal to 110, when acetate was used as main carbon source. It was also shown that a nitrogen feeding during the early exponential phase, coupled with a later nitrogen starvation phase in a two-stage fermentation system allowed a higher final omega-3 recovery. This information could be adopted after the determination of nitrogen content of the DF effluent for its efficient

Table 2

Biomass, Lipid and DHA recovery from the optimized and control fermentations.

Fermentation	Biomass recovery (g/L)	TFA (%DCW)	DHA (%TFA)	DHA recovery (mg/L)
Optimized	3.3	9.0	34.2	101.6
Control	4.4	10.4	35.6	162.9

exploitation. For the industrial utilization of the proposed bio-process, the economic viability was further enhanced by the use of ammonium salts as an economic alternative nitrogen source. Results exhibited a satisfactory assimilation of ammonium by the cells, which led to a relatively small decrease of the final omega-3 production in comparison to the prospect of cost cutback. The potential of conversing a waste stream of a biohydrogen producing process to a substantial amount of DHA, by modifying the culture conditions of the fermentation process, was emphasized in the present study. However, in order for the coupled generation of hydrogen and omega-3 production to be industrially sustainable, a concentrated waste stream rich in VFA is necessary in order to obtain a high cell-density culture and a high DHA recovery.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Angelina Chalima: Writing - original draft, Methodology, Investigation. **George Taxeidis:** Investigation. **Evangelos Topakas:** Conceptualization, Supervision, Writing - review & editing.

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